

OUTLINE

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1. Introduction and overview

The RISIS Patent database (RPD) is designed for the analysis of technological knowledge creation, using patent of invention as a proxy. As a proxy for knowledge creation, a relevant unit of observation is a priority patent application, i.e. the very first patent application, anywhere in the world to protect an invention. RPD focuses on the priority patents that represent the creation of new knowledge, while other non-priority patents describe either technical ameliorations or market extensions and are mobilised as indicators of the importance of the priority patent. The priority date is used to determine the novelty of the invention.

RISIS Patent database derives from the PATSTAT database of the European Patent Office (PATSTAT April 2017 version). It includes 16,406,977 priority patent data applied for from 2000 to 2015 (including artificial priority patents). Before being uploaded in RPD, the initial PATSTAT raw data were quite significantly improved cleaned enriched and harmonised, thanks to the addition of information from other sources and to several methodological developments made during the RISIS project: Filling of information in artificial patents, filling of addresses, geocoding of addresses and their allocation to new geographical units, harmonisation of applicants and their allocation to sectors, ...

Besides the date of the filing and the office where the patent was first filed, we specifically consider in RPD core attributes of priority patents:

- **Their technological content using the standard technology classification and textual sources of information,**
- **The geographical location of inventive activities based on inventors addresses,**
- **The legal organisations that apply for patents (the applicants),**
- **Characteristics linked to the value of the patents.**

RISIS Patent is an accessible and rich data source for research activities in the production of knowledge using patent data. It allows studying the dynamics of knowledge creation along different dimensions: space, actors and technologies. The Risis Patent Database enables to access to these dimensions at a coarse level or at a fine grained level using either usual classification (for technologies, geography) or designing ad-hoc data subsets of patents in specific topics of inventions, for a particular type of institutions in given geographical spaces.

Link to metadata in RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/5/metadata>

Link to documentation in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3342454#.XtjRp4zaYU>

Link to tutorial in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3667571#.Xtii054zaYU>

2. Activities and Developments in the first reporting period

2.1. Maintenance

A complete and stabilised version of the Risis Patent Database was released at M6 (planned M12). It is designed to be user friendly and it is significantly different from the original EPO Patstat database. In order to proxy the knowledge creation, the unit of observation in Risis Patent Database is a priority patent application, i.e. the very first patent application, anywhere in the world to protect an invention. It includes six tables to characterise the priority patents in terms of basic legal information, geography, actors, technologies, values and textual information. All the developments already available at the start of RISIS2 as well as new ones were including. The new developments are: -the addition of the aggregated textual information included in the IPC descriptions, -the improvement of the allocation of the type of applicants (legal entities or persons), -the translation of titles and abstracts in English for documents not already in English in Patstat (except for texts in Russian, Chinese, Japanese or Korean languages), - the geocoding and allocation of addresses to URAs (Urban Rural Area), the partial allocation of actors (legal entities as applicants) to sectors. Matching of legal applicants with firms of CIB2 has been carried out as well as the identification of public organisations. Such a large-scale allocation has been done using the new textual matching tool (PAM system) development at UGE.

2.2. Deepening

The deepening of the RISIS Patent Database aims at improving the picture of the patent output of universities (academic patents). Academic patents can be singled out, either when a university is listed among the applicants, or when an inventor can be identified as being a researcher from a university (academic inventor). In RISIS1, a methodology to retrieve academic patents applied by universities using the ORGREG register was developed. In RISIS2 we will complete the identification of academic patents by identifying the patents including European academic inventors among the inventors for EPO and PCT patents. This will be done according to a methodology already set up for German academic inventors at Fraunhofer ISI linking names of academic authors of publications from SCOPUS with inventors of patents in RISIS Patent Database.

In order to generate a dataset of academic inventors in Europe, several working steps in terms of data generation have to be carried out. To identify academic inventors, we rely on a matching of author names from Scopus with inventor names from PATSTAT. This, however, suffers a problem of homonyms for very common names, e.g. Thomas Müller in Germany, which can immensely bias the results. In order to counteract this effect, there is a system of checks that go beyond the name of the person, i.e. we check whether the patent and the publication are within a similar time window, we check whether the author and inventor live in the same region (NUTS-2) and we check whether the patent and the publication are within a similar technological area via a rough concordance of technology fields in patents and scientific fields in publications.

To accomplish this system of checks, we firstly needed to set up a regionalization of European regions that fits into the standard used in the RISIS2 project. In RISIS2, "Pelias" was developed, which allows a geocoding of addresses in terms of longitude and latitude. Pelias essentially is a search engine for locations worldwide, powered by open data. It turns addresses and place names into geographic coordinates, and vice versa. At its very core, it takes a text input, such as an address or the name of a place, and returns a latitude/longitude location for that location (see <https://github.com/pelias/pelias>)

Setting up Pelias at Fraunhofer ISI thus was a necessary precondition for the identification of academic patents. Besides being a standard in RISIS, it includes a system of cleaning raw

address data. This is necessary, as in Scopus roughly 50% of addresses are in a non-systematic form, i.e. all information on post codes, street names, names of cities are stored within on line of raw text. In earlier studies by Fraunhofer that were targeted towards identifying academic patents in Germany, such cleanings were made manually. However, for Europe as a whole, this was not feasible and therefore an automated method had to be set-up. This is supposed to increase the coverage of academic patents in Europe, as more address data can be taken into account.

The setup of Pelias is rather resource intensive and has recently been finished. After this was completed, Scopus and PATSTAT had to be regionalized with Pelias to generate the longitude/latitude information and create NUTS-2 regions within the data. After that, a first test for the identification for academic patents for Germany has been carried out. Currently, we are comparing this data for Germany to earlier versions to see how good the new identification system works. Once this is finalized, we will publish the data for Germany and identify and cross-check university patents for the other EU countries, starting with France.

In sum, the activities at ISI Fraunhofer are thus 3-4 months behind the initial schedule, which can be attributed to the inclusion of Pelias into our identification system, which allows us to potentially have a higher data quality and be in line with the RISIS standards. Part of the delay can also be attributed to the COVID-19 uptake, which slowed down our progress. However, we are confident to catch up with the original schedule by the end of the year, at the latest.

No deepening activity was carried out at UGE.

2.3. Access and usages

Condensed, content-wise overview on usage/access of the dataset:

The main use of the RPD is the construction of the CIB2 database, another RISIS database that is a subset of priority patents applied by the top corporate R&D performers headquartered worldwide (see documentation of CIB2 for further information) and CINNOB a further development of CIB2 where patent data are aggregated at the firm level. This is done at UGE.

An interesting research using RPD data was carried out at AIT on the structure and dynamics of international co-patenting networks in ICT (<https://zenodo.org/record/3817270#.XuoNXedCRPY>). It shows how international R&D networks in ICT become larger, denser and less centralized, points out the weakening of powerful position of the US and the ongoing catching up of China (see below).

Global R&D collaboration network in ICT

reference : T. Scherngell, C. Rohde, & M. Neulndtner. (2020). Dynamics of global co-patenting networks in ICT: Is China on the way to pass the US?
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3817270>

RPD was fully operational for visits in the beginning of 2020 (but some of them were organised before using a version under construction). Overall, 10 visits were organised (most of them on line). They cover a large set of topics and type of analysis: Analysis of special technologies (Greentech, ICT, Space, Nanocellulose, Pesticides), Analysis of the technological activities of actors (university, regions).

Some projects have combined RPD data with other data available in RISIS: scientific publications (CWTS publications) and EU project (EUPRO) to cover both the basic science and technological development in a given field (the Nanocellulose project is an exemple including patents and publications) or to characterise the overall R&D activities of institutions (European universities).

Transversal issues:

- ▶ Applicants (legal entities) present of RPD are linked to Firm_Reg (Firm_Reg_id allocation) when they are identified as a company belonging to the CIB2 database.
- ▶ Applicants (legal entities) present of RPD are linked to Org_Reg when they are identified as a European university or PRO.
- ▶ Link to documentation in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3342454#.XtjRp4zaYU>
- ▶ Link to tutorial in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3667571#.Xtj054zaYU>

3. Outlook and next steps

- ▶ Maintenance:

No significant new developments in RPD are planned but improving and finalising the current ones are at the agenda of the next months.

It includes: -translating textual information in Russian and in Asian languages, -finalising as much as possible the allocation of legal entities to sector. This will include the matching of applicant names

with VICO and CHEETAH firms using the PAM tool and analysing the residue, - improving the filling of information in the addresses.

A new version of the RISIS Patent Database will be provided in 2021. It will rely on the 2020 PATSTAT version.

► Deepening:

The expected updated timetable for the academic patent dataset is:

- August 2020: Identification of academic patents based on a link between PATSTAT and Scopus employing a Levenshtein matching algorithm and using geo-coding; first countries will be Germany and France as test cases for the method
- September-October 2020: First usable version for all EU-27 countries
- November-December 2020: Updated and approved version for all EU-27 countries

Integration in the RCF depends on RCF developments. It is accepted that Risis Patent Database will be a test for integration.

4. List of milestones and Deliverables (WP5, WP9)

D5.1 - Work plan on Maintenance RPD (October 2019).

D5.2 - First interim report on Maintenance of RISIS core dataset (June 2020) Contribution to the report.

D9.1 - Consolidated work plan on datasets development RPD (December 2019).

The final RPD documentation was provided and uploaded in Zenodo in November 2019 (preliminary version in August 2019).

The RPD tutorial was provided and uploaded in Zenodo in October 2019.

The RPD documentation was uploaded in HAL, the French Open Archive Repository ([hal-02361266](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02361266)).

5. List of accesses

Applicant	Applicant institution	Project Title	Date
Enrico Bergamini	bruegel	Green Industrial Policy: Understanding EU's Regional Low-Carbon Technologies Potential	24.06.2019
Leena Huiku	Aalto University	The identification of research performed at Aalto University around Social Gr... challenges & driven analysis	17.10.2019
Massimiliano Guerini	Politecnico di Milano	An analysis of knowledge production in Europe	16.11.2019
Eleonora Pierucci	Roma Tre University	The geography of European Universities collaborations at NUTS2 level: Patents, Publications, and Project Networks	09.12.2019
Marco Cavallaro	USI Lugano	Participation of Universities of Applied Science in EU Framework Programmes: The research drift as a key driver?	15.12.2019
Charlotte Guillard	UCL London	Knowledge spillovers in Space	08.01.2020
Aliakbar Akbaritabar	DZHW Berlin	Determinants and Effects of Cooperation in Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Research Clusters	18.02.2020
Thomas Scherngell	AIT Vienna	The dynamics of global R&D networks in ICT	10.03.2020
Frédéric Corolléur	Université Grenoble Alpes	Nanocellulose	20.04.2020

Renée van Dis	INRA E-UGE	PhD research (part of the 'PPR: cultiver et proteger autrement')	19.06 .2020
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